

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF USING INVESTMENTS IN AGRICULTURE

Termiz Institute of Agrotechnologies and Innovative Development

Faculty of "Agrologistics and Business",

Teacher of "Agribusiness, accounting and digital technologies" department

Doctoral student of Tashkent International University of Chemistry

Khudaiberdiyeva Nilufar Mengqobilovna

nilumirzo@mail.ru

Abstract: This article examines the peculiarities of the use of investments in agriculture. Specific aspects of the agricultural sector, importance of investments, existing problems and ways to solve them are analyzed. Modern methods and prospects of attracting investments in the industry are considered.

Key words: agriculture, investments, agro-industrial complex, innovative technologies, public-private partnership, diversification, digitization, resource efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is an important branch of the economy of Uzbekistan. It accounts for 28.5% of the country's gross domestic product and provides employment to 49% of the population. At the same time, the industry feels the need for modern technologies and investments. Attracting investments in agriculture and their effective use is important for ensuring the country's food security, improving the living standards of the rural population, and ensuring economic growth.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

During the research, scientific literature, reports of international organizations and legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied on the issue of

investments in agriculture. In particular, according to FAO (2019), every dollar invested in agriculture in developing countries is 2.5-3 times more effective than in other sectors of the economy [1].

Analytical, comparative analysis and statistical data summarization methods were used in the research. The official data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade were analyzed.

RESULTS

The following specific features of the use of investments in agriculture were identified:

- Seasonality. Agricultural production has a seasonal nature, which determines the cyclical nature of investments.
- Dependence on natural and climatic conditions. The effectiveness of investment projects largely depends on weather and climate conditions.
- Long-term character. Many agricultural investments (for example, horticulture, livestock) are of a long-term nature.
- High risk level. Investments in agriculture are associated with high risk due to natural disasters, pests and diseases.
- Dependence on state aid. Agriculture often relies on government subsidies and other support measures.
- Need for innovative technologies. Modern agriculture requires high-tech equipment and advanced agro-technologies.

DISCUSSION

Attracting and effectively using investments in agriculture is a complex and multifaceted process, which includes a number of specific problems and challenges. The uniqueness of this industry is determined by its high dependence on natural and climatic conditions and the high level of risk compared to other sectors of the economy. At the same time, agriculture is a strategically important sector in terms of ensuring the country's food security, increasing the employment of the rural population and making a significant contribution to the gross domestic product.

As stated in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 dated October 23, 2019, "modernization of agriculture, acceleration of its technical and technological re-equipment, improvement of land reclamation, attraction of investments in the sector and introduction of innovative technologies" identified as priorities [2]. This once again confirms the relevance of the issue of using investments in agriculture.

A number of main problems are observed in the process of attracting investments in agriculture and their effective use. One of these is the inadequacy of the infrastructure, with many rural areas lacking essential infrastructure such as modern irrigation systems, roads and electricity. This causes additional costs for investors and reduces the economic efficiency of projects. According to the World Bank, well-developed infrastructure can increase agricultural productivity by 30-40% [4].

Limited financial resources are also a serious problem. Many farms do not have access to credit or cannot borrow because of high interest rates. This limits their investment opportunities and prevents the introduction of modern

technologies. OECD studies show that only 15% of agricultural enterprises in developing countries have full access to formal financial services [5].

Lack of qualified personnel is also an important obstacle in attracting investments in agriculture. Highly qualified specialists are required to use modern agrotechnologies. However, rural areas often lack such specialists. This reduces the efficiency of investments and slows down the introduction of innovative technologies. According to FAO, only 5% of agricultural professionals in developing countries have fully mastered modern technologies [1].

The weak link between production and processing is also a notable problem. Agricultural processing capacities are insufficient or unevenly distributed. This limits farmers' incomes and hinders the development of the product value chain. Khudaiberdiyeva N.M. (2021) noted, "In Uzbekistan, only 10-15% of agricultural products are processed on an industrial scale, this figure is higher than 50% in developed countries" [3].

The underdevelopment of export infrastructure also limits the export of agricultural products and reduces opportunities to enter international markets. As a result, the attractiveness of investments decreases and it becomes difficult to attract foreign investors.

It is desirable to develop a number of directions to solve these problems and effectively use investments in agriculture. Through the development of public-private partnerships, it allows to combine the resources of the public and private sectors for the implementation of infrastructure projects. For example, public-private partnership mechanisms can be used in the construction of irrigation systems, roads and warehouses. This will create a favorable environment for investments and increase the interest of the private sector in agriculture.

According to the World Bank, public-private partnership projects can reduce infrastructure costs in agriculture by 15-20% [4].

It is also important to improve the preferential lending system. It is necessary to develop mechanisms for providing loans to farms on favorable terms. Tools such as government guarantees, subsidized interest rates and long-term loans can be used here. It is also necessary to develop microcredit organizations and financial institutions specialized in agricultural loans. According to OECD recommendations, it is desirable to increase the share of agricultural loans in GDP to at least 3-5% [5].

Improving the personnel training system is also an urgent task. It is necessary to train specialists with modern knowledge and skills in the field of agriculture. For this, it is necessary to revise the educational programs of agricultural higher educational institutions and professional colleges based on modern requirements, strengthen practice-oriented education, and develop international cooperation. It is also important to organize regular training courses for farmers, seminars and trainings on modern agricultural technologies. According to FAO experts, improving the skills of agricultural specialists can increase productivity by 25-30% [1].

Through the development of agro-industrial clusters, it is possible to strengthen the connection between production and processing, extend the chain of value creation and increase the efficiency of investments. Within the framework of clusters, effective cooperation is established between research institutes, producers, processors and trading companies. This allows introducing innovations and increasing competitiveness. Khudaiberdiyeva N.M. (2021) noted that "agro-

industry clusters allow to increase the level of processing of agricultural products by 2-3 times and significantly increase the volume of exports" [3].

Digitization and introduction of innovative technologies is also an important area of effective use of investments in agriculture. "Intelligent agriculture" technologies should be widely used. In this direction, the use of modern technologies such as precision farming, artificial intelligence, big data analysis, drones and robotics are important. Digital technologies enable efficient use of resources, increase productivity and reduce negative impact on the environment. According to the World Bank, the implementation of digital technologies can increase agricultural productivity by up to 70% [4].

Improvement of the insurance system also serves to increase the efficiency of the use of investments in agriculture. Considering the high risks in agriculture, it is necessary to develop effective insurance mechanisms. This reduces risks for investors and ensures financial stability. It is desirable to introduce government-subsidized agricultural insurance programs, develop weather index-based insurance products, and provide incentives for insurance companies.

Increasing the export potential is also one of the important tasks. To support the export of agricultural products, it is necessary to create the necessary infrastructure, develop the certification system in accordance with international standards, and improve marketing strategies. It is important to give tax incentives and subsidies to exporting farms, and to provide information and consulting support when entering foreign markets. According to the OECD, export-oriented agricultural enterprises have 20-30% higher profitability than domestic market-oriented enterprises [5].

The introduction of resource-efficient technologies also helps to use investments efficiently. In the conditions of shortage of water resources, it is necessary to widely introduce modern irrigation systems such as drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation. Also, the use of renewable energy sources, the use of waste-free technologies and the development of organic farming are important. This allows not only efficient use of resources, but also ensures environmental stability and increases the competitiveness of agricultural products.

Support for scientific research activities also serves to increase the efficiency of the use of investments in agriculture. It is necessary to further improve the activity of scientific research institutes in the field of agriculture, to strengthen their material and technical base and to expand international cooperation. It is necessary to strengthen fundamental and applied research in such directions as creating crop varieties adapted to climate change, growing plants resistant to diseases and pests, and developing technologies for increasing soil fertility. According to the FAO, a 1% increase in agricultural R&D spending can increase productivity by 6-12% [1].

CONCLUSION

The specific characteristics of the use of investments in agriculture are related to seasonality, dependence on natural and climatic conditions, long-term nature, high risk level, dependence on state support and the need for innovative technologies. Taking into account these features, an integrated approach is necessary to attract and effectively use investments in agriculture.

By developing public-private partnership, improving the preferential lending system, modernizing the personnel training system, developing agro-industry

clusters and accelerating digitization processes, it is possible to increase investment attractiveness in agriculture and ensure sustainable development of the sector.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. FAO. (2019). The State of Food and Agriculture 2019. Moving forward on food loss and waste reduction. Rome.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. PF-5853 "On approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030".
3. Khudaiberdiyeva N.M. (2021). Development directions of investment activity in agriculture. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies", issue 3.
4. World Bank. (2020). Enabling the Business of Agriculture 2019. Washington, DC: World Bank.
5. OECD. (2021). Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation 2021. OECD Publishing, Paris.